

STUDIES OF JOSHI EFFECT IN HYDROGEN

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Production of the Joshi effect in H_2 under ozoniser excitation has been studied in respect of (i) gas pressure (20-200 mm.), (ii) temperature (15° - 55°), (iii) frequency and intensity of incident light, (iv) applied potential (0.67-2.13 kV), (v) frequency of A. C. supply, and (vi) ageing. Under favourable conditions, the system shows Joshi effect of as much as 50% current diminution under but visible light. As generalised by Joshi, the relative Joshi effect, $-\% \Delta i$, is (numerically) maximum at V_m , the threshold potential and decreases thereafter. Gas pressure shows a limiting influence. Increase of (ii) and (v) decreases, while that of (iii) increases the effect. Moderate 'ageing' under the discharge due to a high potential, followed by allowing the system to stand over for limited periods, enhances the effect. Evidence has been adduced to show that the Joshi effect is not a consequence of selective absorption, nor due to destruction of metastable atoms under irradiation. These findings are in accord with Joshi's general theory of the phenomenon.

The discovery of the Joshi effect is the outcome of a programme of research initiated in the chemical laboratories of the Benares Hindu University on the study of the behaviour of gases, elemental and compound, when subjected to silent and other type of electrical discharge (Joshi, *Chem. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; Joshi and Narasimhan, *ibid.*, 1940, 9, 536; Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75). The general finding of Joshi's that (i) a gas is characterised by a minimum threshold potential, V_m at/near which it breaks down as a dielectric and shows a sudden increase in conductivity (Joshi, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 147), (ii) that in a compound gas, a reaction is induced only when the applied potential equals or exceeds V_m (*loc. cit.*), and (iii) that irradiation of the reaction vessel, which is an all-glass Siemens' ozoniser or a semi-ozoniser of wire-in-cylinder type, results in a rise in V_m of the system, led Joshi to the anticipation and discovery of the Joshi effect, viz., that i , the discharge current at a definite applied potential, shows an instantaneous and reversible variation (usually a decrease), Δi on irradiation (Joshi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 389). Most of the early work was confined to Cl_2 in which the effect was first observed and in which it was considerable, being as much as 93-95% of i under optimum conditions (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, 153, 434). Subsequent investigation of other systems has led to the belief that the effect is considerable in the other halogens also, and is in the order: $Cl_2 > Br_2 > I_2$ and that it is practically negligible in other gases such as H_2 , N_2 , air, etc. (Joshi and Deshmukh, *Nature*, 1941, 147, 806) and metallic vapours such as Hg.

Recent work with improved technique as regards current detection and measurement, which has resulted in the use of sensitive galvanometers actuated by metal oxide rectifiers or thermionic valves of different types, and the careful examination of the influence of a number of factors, which control and determine the magnitude of the Joshi effect, (*vide infra*) have revealed the occurrence of the effect to a marked extent in almost all gases, both elemental and compound, and metallic vapours, e.g., O_2 , HCl, NO_2 , air, SO_2 , H_2 , water vapour, NH_3 , Hg, Na, K, S, Se, As, etc. From a study of the nature and magni-

tude of the Joshi effect in the halogens and other gases, and its dependence on a number of electrical factors and the nature of irradiation etc., Joshi has advanced a theory for the phenomenon (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25 ; *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19). The theory contemplates a close connection between the Joshi effect and the 'electron affinity' of the gas, which is one of its chief determinants. Whilst then the occurrence of a pronounced Joshi effect in the halogens, which possess a large electron affinity (3.22 to 3.70 e.v.), is easily understood, contrary to the preliminary results, an appreciable Joshi effect also in H_2 is to be anticipated since its electron affinity, 0.76 e.v., is not inconsiderable (Massey, "Negative Ions", The Cambridge Physical Tracts, 1938 ; Glockler, *Phys. Rev.*, 1934, 48, 111).

Preliminary work by the author (Visvanathan and Raghavan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 29A, 98) on H_2 under silent electric discharge at 500 cycles frequency has indicated that the gas shows no Joshi effect at pressures less than 252 mm., while at 252 mm. it gives a positive effect of 400% just below V_m . While the *fresh* gas at 50 mm. shows no Joshi effect, 'ageing' at an applied potential of 0.40 kV for different periods produces first the negative effect of small magnitude, about 5% decrease of the discharge current in the dark ; as the time of ageing increases, the system develops larger and larger positive effect which ultimately reaches the high value of about 8 times the photoincrease of the discharge current. Admixture of H_2 with Br_2 which taken alone gives a marked negative Joshi effect, which is to be anticipated from its large electron affinity, modifies the behaviour of Br_2 so that the greater the amount of H_2 in the mixture, the larger is the positive effect observed.

In view of the above interesting behaviour of 'aged' and of admixed H_2 with regard to the production of the Joshi effect, it was thought desirable to study comprehensively the production of the phenomenon in pure H_2 with a careful appraisal of the influence of the various factors which affect it viz., (i) applied potential and gas pressure, (ii) ageing of the system and frequency of the A. C. supply, (iii) intensity and (iv) frequency of the incident light, and (v) temperature, for which there is no information in the literature on the subject except the preliminary communication by the author. Since increase of frequency of the A. C. supply is found to reduce the magnitude of the Joshi effect (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67), alternating current of 50 cycles per second has been employed in the present investigation as against 500 cycles used earlier.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus (Fig. 1) consists essentially of three parts, viz., (i) arrangement for the electrolytic preparation, drying and storage of H_2 ; (ii) discharge tube and electrical connections, and (iii) arrangement for the irradiation of the ozoniser. Since the apparatus is essentially the same as described in some of the previous publications on the Joshi effect, its full description is not given here. Only important points in which the present set-up of the apparatus differs from the others are mentioned.

Preparation and Storage of the Gas.—A saturated solution of barium peroxide (Merck, ex. pure) was prepared with CO_2 -free water and electrolysed in a U tube A

one limb of which containing the negative electrode at which H_2 was evolved, being about twice as long as the other. The electrodes were of platinum foils and the current was adjusted so as to give a slow evolution of H_2 and O_2 . The gas was led through drying tubes *B* containing fused $CaCl_2$ and P_2O_5 and stored in the gas holder, *C*.

Discharge Tube and Electrical Connections.—An all-glass Siemens' ozoniser was used as the discharge vessel. Single phase alternating potentials of frequency of 50 cycles per second, obtained from a rotary converter worked off the 220-volt D. C. mains, were stepped up by means of a transformer and maintained at the desired value by regulation of the external resistance, *R*, of the primary circuit. One terminal of the transformer was earthed, while the other, the high tension terminal, was connected to the inner electrode of the ozoniser. The circuit was completed by connecting the outer electrode to earth through the current-measuring device, viz., a metal oxide rectifier and a sensitive mirror galvanometer provided with a shunt of non-inductive resistance made of straight silver wire. The deflexions of the galvanometer, as a measure of the discharge current, were read from a scale bent in the form of an arc of radius of about one meter from the galvanometer.

FIG. 1

Irradiation of the Ozoniser.—The ozoniser was irradiated by a system of two 200-Watt and one 80-Watt bulbs which were connected in series with a resistance by the adjustment of which a constant potential of 180 volts was applied to the bulbs in order

to maintain the intensity of illumination constant. The bulbs were enclosed in a wooden box, the side facing the ozoniser being of the nature of a shutter ; the ozoniser could thus be irradiated or kept in dark as desired.

Influence of Applied Potential and Gas Pressure

H₂ was introduced into the ozoniser at a pressure of 200 mm. and exposed to a very low applied potential which was raised gradually to higher values. The current in the earlier stages, as measured by the milliammeter and the deflexion of the galvanometer, was very small, almost negligible. When the applied potential reached a critical value viz., the threshold potential, V_m, there was a sudden, large increase in the current and the gas began to glow faintly. Irradiation of the ozoniser containing the gas produced no change in the current at potentials less than V_m, while at V_m, i₀, the discharge current in the dark, showed an instantaneous and reversible decrease to i_z, the current under irradiation. The above observations are in line with those reported from these laboratories (Joshi, *Nature*, 1944, ~~154~~, 147; *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 253, 278; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 225). The net Joshi effect, Δi (= i_z - i₀) and the relative Joshi effect, %Δi (= 100Δi/i₀) have been calculated. In general, the discharge current ranged between 0.01 and 0.3 milliamperes for the range of applied potentials studied. Since it was not possible to measure accurately the current changes, especially at low potentials, owing to limitations of the available milliammeter, i₀, i_z and hence Δi were measured in terms of the deflexions of the galvanometer, from which the relative Joshi effect, %Δi, has been calculated. In the present investigation, H₂ gave only the negative effect, -Δi and -%Δi and for purposes of comparison their numerical values alone have been employed.

The variation of the Joshi effect with the pressure of the gas was studied by abstracting from the ozoniser hydrogen till the pressure was reduced to the next required value viz., 150 mm. at which pressure the potential variation of the Joshi effect was again studied. Thus, the different pressures at which such studies were made were obtained by pumping out part of the gas in stages till a pressure of 15 mm. was reached. The pressures thus studied are 200, 150, 124, 108, 90, 80, 70, 60, 50, 40, 30 and 20 mm. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Potential variation of relative Joshi effect, %Δi, in hydrogen.

(a) p _{H₂} = 200 mm.		(b) p _{H₂} = 150 mm.		(c) p _{H₂} = 124 mm.		(d) p _{H₂} = 108 mm.	
kV.	-%Δi.	kV.	-%Δi.	kV.	-%Δi.	kV.	-%Δi.
1.34	9.5	1.07	15.8	1.07	20.5	0.67	22.8
1.60	1.7	1.34	6.1	1.34	7.8	1.07	22.1
1.87	0.5	1.60	1.7	1.60	2.4	1.34	13.4
		1.87	0.5	1.87	1.4	1.60	6.0
						1.87	3.4

TABLE I (contd.)

(e) $p_{H_2} = 90$ mm		(f) $p_{H_2} = 80$ mm		(g) $p_{H_2} = 70$ mm.		(h) $p_{H_2} = 60$ mm.	
kV.	$-\% \Delta i$.	kV.	$-\% \Delta i$	kV	$-\% \Delta i$.	kV.	$-\% \Delta i$.
0.67	19.8	0.67	20.6	0.67	23.8	0.67	38.7
1.07	14.5	1.07	12.6	1.07	12.3	1.07	28.9
1.34	8.9	1.34	8.3	1.34	6.9	1.34	14.6
1.60	6.3	1.60	4.5	1.60	4.2	1.60	6.8
1.74	5.2					1.60	4.6
(i) $p_{H_2} = 50$ mm.		(j) $p_{H_2} = 40$ mm		(k) $p_{H_2} = 30$ mm.		(l) $p_{H_2} = 20$ mm.	
kV	$-\% \Delta i$.	kV.	$-\% \Delta i$	kV.	$-\% \Delta i$	kV.	$-\% \Delta i$.
0.54	31.6	0.54	50.0	0.54	48.4	0.54	24.2
0.67	26.3	0.67	34.5	0.67	33.8	0.67	1.7
1.07	12.8	1.07	16.9	1.07	9.9	1.07	0
1.34	7.4	1.34	7.2	1.34	5.1	1.34	0
1.60	3.7	1.60	3.0	1.60	2.6		

It is seen from Table I that for any particular pressure of the gas, the relative effect, $\% \Delta i$, is (numerically) maximum at the lowest potential indicated viz., the threshold potential, V_m and decreases as the potential increases. This characteristic behaviour of the relative Joshi effect has been observed in numerous other systems as well (Joshi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **22A**, 389).

The variation of $\% \Delta i$ with the pressure of the gas may be illustrated by the following readings.

Pressure (mm.):	200	150	124	108	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20
At 1.34 kV, $\% \Delta i$:	9.5	6.8	7.8	13.4	8.9	8.3	6.9	6.8	7.4	7.2	5.1	0
At 1.60 kV, $\% \Delta i$:	1.7	1.7	2.4	6.0	6.3	4.5	4.2	4.6	3.7	3.0	2.6	0

While maximum effect is obtained at 108 mm. of the gas at both the applied potentials, the influence of the latter is brought out by the fact that $\% \Delta i$ is less at 1.60 kV than at 1.34 kV at all pressures. Below a pressure of 30 mm. the gas shows no Joshi effect.

Instead of comparing the values of $\% \Delta i$ at any arbitrary applied potential, they, in accordance with the concept of 'corresponding potentials' developed by the author in his paper on Joshi effect in air (unpublished), are compared at the threshold potential, V_m of the various pressures; the results stand out more significantly. Thus,

Pressure of H_2 :	200	150	124	108	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20
$-\% \Delta i$ at V_m :	9.5	15.8	20.5	22.8	19.8	20.6	23.8	38.7	31.6	50.0	48.4	24.2

TABLE III

Influence of ageing on the relative Joshi effect in hydrogen.

(a) Pressure of H ₂ =80 mm.				(b) Pressure of H ₂ =70 mm.				(c) Pressure of H ₂ =50 mm.						
kV.	←-----→			-----%Δi				-----→						
	After ageing for 1 hr at 5.5 kV.	After 4 hrs.	After 16 hrs.	At 500 cycles frequency	After 24 hrs.	Soon after previous study	At 500 cycles frequency.	After ageing for 1 hr. at 5.5 kV.	After 16 hrs.	Soon after previous study.	After 5 hrs. ageing for 1 hr at 5.5 kV.	After 12 hrs. ageing for 2 hrs.		
0.67	14.8	25.0	25.0	kV was varied 0.27 to 0.54 -%Δi varied between 4.8 & 0.5	22.5	19.6	kV was varied 0.27 to 0.54 -%Δi varied between 5.6 & 2.6	18.0	18.5	19.3	20.0	20.0	27.4	20.7
0.80	11.7	29.6	31.5		26.1	25.6		17.8	—	15.6	16.9	12.8	—	13.5
0.94	11.7	16.8	21.1		20.8	18.9		14.4	17.0	—	14.0	—	13.7	—
1.07	8.8	14.8	14.3		12.8	15.5		9.5	15.8	10.1	10.2	10.1	11.6	8.9
1.20	7.7	11.8	10.1		10.1	9.7		7.3	9.3	8.5	8.1	6.7	7.9	7.4
1.34	6.4	8.4	8.6		8.0	7.6		5.6	7.0	4.1	4.8	5.0	5.8	4.2
1.47	1.9	5.2	6.4		5.2	6.2		4.6	5.4	2.8	4.1	3.9	4.9	3.0
1.60	0.6	1.1	4.0		1.3	4.0		2.6	3.1	—	3.0	3.2	3.2	2.8

On ageing it at 5.5 kV for 1 hour, the magnitude of the effect is reduced to 14.8% at V_m . The same is the case also at the higher potentials. When the gas is allowed to stand for 3 hours, the magnitude of the effect increases to 29.6% which is more than that given by even the fresh gas. An interval of 16 hours augments the value still further to 31.5%.

The influence of the frequency of the A.C. supply was incidentally studied by subjecting the gas of the previous experiments to applied potentials in the range of 0.27 to 0.54 kV of frequency of 500 cycles per second. Under these electrical conditions also, the system shows only negative Joshi effect; but its magnitude is considerably smaller than that for 50 cycles frequency and varies in the range of 4.8 to 0.5%. Results obtained for the potential variation of the gas once again at 50 cycles frequency, after allowing the gas to stand for 24 hours, show a diminution in the magnitude of the effect, viz., 26.1 which still is larger than that for the fresh gas.

A reduction in the pressure of the gas to the new value of 70 mm. is accompanied by a slight reduction in the Joshi effect as well. Exposure of the gas to potentials of 500 cycles frequency gives %Δi varying in the range of 5.7 to 1.1, which again emphasises the striking contrast in the influence of the frequency difference on the production of the Joshi effect. When the gas is next exposed to 5.5 kV of 50 cycles frequency and immediately after, the potential variation of the Joshi effect studied, high values characteristic of the lower frequency are obtained for %Δi. Allowing the gas to stand for 16 hours brings about, as before, an increase in the magnitude of the Joshi effect.

The above observations regarding the influence of ageing apply *in toto* to the case when the gas pressure is reduced to 50 mm.

In another series of experiments, H₂ at 70 mm. was aged at an applied potential of 5.5 kV of 50 cycles frequency for half an hour, after which the potential variation of

Fig. 2

TABLE IV

Influence of ageing on the potential variation of the Joshi effect.

(a) Pressure of H₂=70 mm.

(b) Pressure of H₂=96 mm.

kV.	- % Δf						kV.	- % Δf		
	After ageing at 5.5 kV.	After 24 hours.	After 48 hours.	After 72 hours.	After 96 hours.	After 120 hours.		After ageing at 5.5 kV.	After 24 hours.	After 48 hours.
0.91	36.5	21.4	23.3	27.8	1.7	—	0.91	19.8	12.0	11.3
1.07	43.0	48.9	58.9?	45.7	4.0	—	1.07	43.1	23.5	29.7
1.23	42.9	22.2	21.2	29.2	4.1	—	1.23	—	—	—
1.33	17.8	14.5	12.8	14.7	1.7	2.4	1.33	31.1	13.2	9.3
1.49	17.6	15.4	12.1	8.3	1.3	2.5	1.49	18.0	—	—
1.60	—	—	—	4.8	—	1.8	1.60	17.5	—	—

the Joshi effect was observed in this gas. This was repeated at intervals of 24 hours during which the gas was allowed to stand. The pressure of the gas was then raised to 96 mm. by admitting fresh gas and observations similar to the above taken. Table IV contains some typical data obtained in the above series of experiments.

It is found, in general, that the magnitude of the effect in the gas allowed to stand for a prolonged period shows a progressive diminution. Thus, H_2 at 70 mm. after a rest of 96 hours shows a large drop from 45.7 to 4.0%. The same feature is observed also in regard to the higher pressure studied, viz., 96 mm.

The above results lead to the conclusion that while allowing the gas to stand for moderate periods after ageing at a large applied potential results in improving the performance of the system with regard to the production of the Joshi effect, very large intervals extending into days exert a deleterious effect and the system loses its ability to show the Joshi effect to any marked extent. Such a behaviour of the gas points to an interaction between the gas and the electrode surface which may result in the formation of "a variable adsorption-like boundary layer", photochemically active, as postulated by Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 175; 1947, 16, 19) and which is the main seat of the phenomenon of the Joshi effect.

It is interesting to compare the influence of ageing observed in the present system with that in other systems. Deo (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 76) found that in the case of an 'aged' ozoniser, that is, one which had been in use for work on the Joshi effect in Cl_2 over one and half years showed no time variation of the effect, while in a fresh ozoniser i_0 and i_L , as also Δi and $\% \Delta i$, increased considerably during a continued exposure to discharge. The 'ageing' effect in Cl_2 was more pronounced under X-rays (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 18, 278) which produced a permanent decrease in the magnitude of the Joshi effect on exposing the ozoniser to the applied potential for half an hour. Goyal (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 203) found that in Cl_2 'ageing' stabilises the discharge current, increasing markedly the Joshi effect over a wide range of applied potentials. Ramanamurti (*ibid.*, 1948, 26, 255) has made kinetic studies of the progressive development of Δi during ageing and finds that it follows the equation for the 'first order' reactions. The results obtained for Hg vapour (B. N. Prasad, unpublished results) are very striking in that the system initially gives no Joshi effect but develops it on ageing; the magnitude of the effect increases to a maximum on continued ageing, at which value it remains stationary thereafter.

It is suggested tentatively from a review of the results available for the influence of ageing on the production of the Joshi effect that easily adsorbed and reactive gases such as Cl_2 , Br_2 , I_2 , O_2 and Hg develop or give a progressively increasing value of $\% \Delta i$ reaching ultimately a maximum, while the 'permanent' gases such as H_2 , air N_2 etc., which undergo little adsorption, are not susceptible to 'ageing' influence to the same extent and in fact, lose the capacity to show the effect after prolonged ageing.

Influence of Intensity of Incident Light

That the Joshi effect is sensitive to changes in the intensity of irradiation has been observed in Cl_2 (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 35; Deo, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1944, 18, 83).

In view of the observation of positive Joshi effect, *i. e.*, a photoincrease in the current in H_2 (*loc. cit.*) and a number of other systems under certain conditions, a close connection between the photoelectric effect and the Joshi effect may be contemplated. It is known that in vacuum cells, photoelectric emission is strictly proportional to the intensity of light, while in gas-filled tubes subjected to electric fields, strong enough to produce ionisation by collision in the gas, the current may be expected to increase more than linearly with the intensity of irradiation. Hence it appeared instructive to study the influence of the intensity of the incident light on the magnitude of the Joshi effect.

Three different intensities of the irradiating light were obtained from three systems A, B, C of white incandescent bulbs in the following way. System A consisted of two 200-Watt bulbs and one 80-Watt bulb; B, of one 200-Watt bulb and one 80-Watt bulb; and C, of one 200-Watt bulb. These bulbs, rated for 220 volts, were worked at 180 volts which was kept constant by adjustment of a resistance in series. The actual intensities of the systems A, B and C were therefore in the ratio 307.2 : 179.2 : 128, *i. e.*, 2.4 : 1.4 : 1.

H_2 was admitted into the ozoniser at a pressure of 205 mm. and the potential variation of the Joshi effect of the system observed when the ozoniser was irradiated by the three systems of irradiation, one after the other. Two pressures of the gas were studied and the data obtained are shown in Table V.

TABLE V

Influence of intensity of irradiation on the relative Joshi effect in hydrogen.

kV	205 mm.			156 mm.			107 mm.			75 mm.			55 mm.			40 mm.			30 mm.		
	% Δi			% Δi			% Δi			% Δi			% Δi			% Δi			% Δi		
	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.
0.67										4.0	—	—	6.5	4.3	2.2	15.0	12.5	10.0	14.6	12.2	9.8
0.94										8.0	6.7	5.3	7.5	6.3	5.2	8.3	6.9	5.5	7.1	6.6	5.9
1.07							2.8	2.2	1.4	13.0	11.1	10.4	6.5	6.0	5.5	5.0	4.0	3.5	6.0	5.0	4.5
1.20				4.0	3.0	2.0	7.2	4.8	3.6	7.5	6.6	5.6	—	—	—	4.5	3.7	3.3	3.9	3.5	3.0
1.34				8.4	7.2	6.0	6.3	5.6	5.2	6.0	5.3	5.0	4.7	4.0	3.4	3.0	2.3	2.0	2.3	2.0	1.8
1.47	4.0	2.9	2.0	8.8	5.6	4.0	6.6	5.7	5.4	4.3	3.8	3.2	3.3	2.8	2.5	2.3	1.7	1.4	1.8	1.5	1.2
1.60	4.7	3.9	3.5	7.1	6.0	4.2	6.5	4.5	4.2	3.8	3.4	3.1	2.7	2.0	1.8	1.7	1.2	1.0	1.6	1.4	1.2
1.73	4.3	3.2	2.6	6.5	4.8	3.8	5.3	4.2	3.9	3.3	2.9	2.7	2.4	2.0	1.8	1.6	1.2	1.0	1.2	1.0	0.8
1.87	4.0	3.5	2.0	7.0	3.7	3.3	The relative intensities of the three sources of irradiation were in the ratio of A : B : C :: 2.4 : 1.4 : 1														
2.00	3.5	3.1	2.6																		
2.13	3.5	3.1	2.6																		

It is evident that the magnitude of the Joshi effect increases with the intensity of irradiation; but the variation is not linear. For low values % Δi appears to be linear with the intensity of irradiation. But as % Δi takes on higher values, its variation with the intensity of light becomes less than linear and tends to show saturation at higher intensities.

Influence of Frequency of Incident Light

Work on Cl_2 has shown that the Joshi effect is markedly sensitive to the various spectral regions of the irradiating light and the magnitude of the effect for the different regions of same intensity is in the order : white $>$ violet $>$ green $>$ red (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 35, 317; Deo, *Science & Culture*, 1944, 9, 252). Even when the red region had an appreciably larger intensity than violet, $\% \Delta i$ was larger for violet than for green or red. Thus it appears that frequency and not intensity of the irradiating light is the more important determinant of the phenomenon. But since the light used viz., the violet band contains the region which is selectively absorbed by Cl_2 , it could not be asserted without any ambiguity whether the Joshi effect is the result of selective absorption or frequency effect. H_2 , unlike Cl_2 and other gases, is known to be under ordinary conditions the most transparent gas. Even the very short waves, discovered by Schumann, which are powerfully absorbed by other gases, are freely transmitted by hydrogen. It appeared therefore interesting to study the role of frequency of the incident light in such a gas in regard to the production of the Joshi effect.

Different frequency regions of the irradiating light were obtained by the use of glass filters in front of the moving shutter of the box enclosing the bulbs. The transmission limits of the filters, as determined by a Hilger constant deviation spectrograph, were found to be as Violet, 4750 - 4000 Å; Green, 5775 - 5070 Å; Red, 7070 - 6070 Å; White, 7800 - 3700 Å.

H_2 was taken at pressures in the range of 50-20 mm. At each pressure the potential variation of the Joshi effect under irradiation of the ozoniser with the different frequency band was observed. Typical results selected out of several series of such data representing a wide range of exciting conditions are indicated in Table VI.

It is seen that at all applied potentials and pressures of the gas, the order of the magnitude of the Joshi effect is white $>$ violet $>$ green $\geq$ red. In the last column under each pressure is given the sum total of $\% \Delta i$ produced individually by the violet, green and red radiations. In every case the total exceeds the value for white light in spite of the fact that the range of frequencies transmitted by the three light filters is much less than that due to white light. This points to a saturation effect whereby the Joshi effect due to simultaneous irradiations in different spectral regions is less than the sum of the corresponding $\% \Delta i$ produced separately.

The extreme transparency of H_2 has been referred to. Hydrogen gas in the sun and stars shows strong absorption coincident with the emission lines seen when the gas is excited by electrical discharges in vacuum tubes. Attempts to reproduce these absorption lines in the laboratory have shown that absorption takes place only when the gas is in a state of luminiscence. Pflüger (*Ann. Physik*, 1907, 24, 515) by exciting H_2 at low pressure in a capillary tube by powerful electrical discharge from an induction coil and exposing H_2 , contained in a large tube connected to the same electrical circuit, to the glow of hydrogen in the capillary tube was able to observe the red line distinctly reversed. Soon after, Ladenburg and Loria (*Verh. deutsch. phys. Ges.*, 1908, 10, 858) using a similar arrangement reversed both the red and green lines. It is thus seen that hydrogen absorbs the H_α and H_β lines only when it is power-

TABLE VI

Influence of frequency of incident light on the relative Joshi effect.

Applied potential kV.	←----- %ΔI -----→					Violet +green +red.
	White.	Violet.	Green.	Red.		
Pressure of hydrogen = 50 mm.						
0.67	23.5	13.8	11.6	8.7		34.1
1.07	11.7	7.3	6.3	3.8		17.2
1.34	4.8	4.2	3.8	2.2		10.1
1.60	3.3	2.9	2.7	1.5		7.1
Pressure of hydrogen = 40 mm.						
0.67	29.3	16.0	15.1	9.7		40.8
1.07	12.8	7.5	7.0	4.4		18.0
1.34	5.4	4.0	3.4	2.2		9.6
1.60	3.6	2.8	2.5	1.6		6.9
Pressure of hydrogen = 30 mm.						
0.67	24.0	14.0	13.0	9.0		35.0
1.07	10.4	6.8	6.1	4.4		17.3
1.34	5.0	3.8	3.5	2.2		9.5
1.60	3.2	2.4	2.0	1.0		5.4
Pressure of hydrogen = 25 mm.						
0.67	21.3	15.6	13.9	10.0		39.5
1.07	12.0	6.3	5.8	4.5		16.6
1.34	4.3	3.3	3.0	2.3		8.6
1.60	2.6	2.2	1.8	1.3		5.2
Pressure of hydrogen = 20 mm.						
0.67	16.5	12.9	11.4	8.3		32.6
1.07	5.2	4.3	4.0	2.6		10.9
1.34	2.0	1.4	1.3	1.1		5.8
1.60	1.2	0.8	0.7	0.5		3.0

fully excited at low pressures. Lambrey and Chalonge (*Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 1057) have observed that if potentials of 2 to 3 kV are applied to a tube containing H_2 under 2.5 mm., a continuous spectrum is obtained extending from the red into the Schumann region. The H_α ray is visible, but not the H_β or H_γ rays. The spectrum is stable for at least 5 minutes.

Now, in the present experiments, H_2 was taken at comparatively very high pressures, viz., 20 to 50 mm. and excited at potentials intended to give large values of the Joshi

effect; hence the applied potentials were not far removed from V_m . In these circumstances, H_2 will not be in a condition to show selective absorption. The occurrence of the Joshi effect under all frequencies of the irradiating light and especially the magnitude of the effect being in the order: violet > green > red, makes it clear that the effect is *not* the result of selective absorption but is a frequency or quantum phenomenon and that of the two factors, intensity and frequency which influence the magnitude of the effect, the latter is the more important determinant.

Influence of Temperature

It is known that the photoelectric effect is not influenced by temperature. Since the Joshi effect also is a photo-phenomenon, it is of interest to investigate the influence of temperature on its production.

For experiments reported in this Section, the ozoniser was enclosed in a box lined with asbestos internally and heated electrically by means of coils of resistance wire fixed along the walls of the box. On the outer and inner electrolytes showing a steady temperature at the required value, studies of the potential variation of the Joshi effect were carried out. The range of temperature investigated was from 15° to 55° . The room temperature was 30° ; after a study had been made at a different temperature, readings for the potential variations of the Joshi effect were taken at the room temperature. Such a procedure helped to disentangle any effect due to 'ageing' from that due to temperature variation. The data are given in Table VII (cf., Fig 3). The temperatures are indicated in the order in which they were varied.

TABLE VII

Influence of temperature on the relative Joshi effect.

Pressure of hydrogen = 90 mm.

Applied potential kV.	←----- % ΔI at temperature -----→							
	30° .	47° .	30° .	55° .	30° .	20° .	30° .	15° .
0.54	—	—	—	—	7.0	4.7	11.1	14.1
0.80	6.5	6.8	7.1	6.2	14.2	18.3	19.1	23.3
0.91	5.2	7.3	15.9	12.7	23.7	24.9	27.8	24.6
1.07	17.1	15.9	17.0	14.0	17.9	17.9	16.0	15.9
1.17	17.0	13.3	17.5	12.8	13.9	14.4	13.5	13.3
1.28	13.3	10.7	12.2	7.4	13.2	14.7	11.7	12.1
1.33	11.1	9.2	10.6	6.9	11.8	11.9	12.5	10.8
1.39	9.7	7.0	9.7	6.3	—	9.6	10.7	10.2
1.44	9.8	7.6	9.1	5.5	9.4	9.7	9.1	9.5
1.49	10.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

In general it is found that with increase of temperature, $\% \Delta i$ shows an appreciable diminution in value. For example, at 0.80 kV, the values of $\% \Delta i$ at 30°, 47°, 55°, 20° and 15° are 6.5, 6.8, 6.2, 18.3 and 23.3 respectively, while at a higher potential, say 1.33 kV, they are 11.1, 9.2, 6.9, 11.9 and 10.8 respectively. The values of $\% \Delta i$ obtained at the room temperature immediately after a set of readings had been taken at a different temperature are seen to be not quite constant for any definite potential. This is especially so at lower potentials. This is to be attributed to the effect of ageing which thus seems to affect the magnitude of the Joshi effect more at lower than at higher potentials.

Since the Joshi effect is found to be maximum at/near V_m and diminishes as V increases, it may be inferred from the fact that $\% \Delta i$ at a particular potential decreases as the temperature increases, that V_m of the system decreases and hence the effective applied potential ($V - V_m$) increases with increase of temperature. This may be brought about in two ways, viz., (a) the electronic velocity may increase, or/and (b) the conductivity of the glass walls of the ozoniser may increase at higher temperatures. But it is known that the electronic mobility is independent of temperature. If the conductivity of the glass walls increases appreciably with temperature, an increase in the current i_b at constant applied potential may be expected. But it is seen from Table VIII, where the currents i_b corresponding to various applied potentials at the different temperatures are given, that over the range of temperatures studied, viz., 15° to 55°, i_b remains nearly constant. This is more apparent at the higher than at the lower potentials where the ageing effect interferes with the constancy of i_b . Thus, temperature is found to have no influence on i_b but affects i_e in such a way that a decrease in the net and relative Joshi effect results with increase of temperature. This points to some sort of a conditioned surface capable of responding to the incident light.

TABLE VIII

Discharge current at different temperatures.

Applied potential kV.	Pressure of hydrogen=90 mm.							
	Discharge current in milliamps at							
	30°.	47°.	30°.	55°.	30°.	20°.	30°.	15°.
0.51	0.010	0.010	0.015	0.020	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
0.80	.025	.025	.025	.035	.040	.040	.050	.050
0.91	.055	.055	.070	.070	.090	.085	.085	.085
1.07	.130	.130	.130	.140	.130	.130	.130	.125
1.17	.165	.165	.160	.170	.160	.155	.160	.150
1.28	.190	.195	.195	.200	.190	.180	.195	.180
1.33	.210	.210	.210	.220	.200	.200	.210	.200
1.39	.230	.230	.225	.235	—	.210	.225	.215
1.44	.250	.250	.245	.255	.225	.225	.240	.230

Numerous workers have shown that the classical photoelectric effect is not influenced by temperature changes; the temperature has been varied from -190° to 800°. But great care had to be taken to keep the photoelectric surface absolutely clean and

outgassed by heating. Ladenburg (*Verh. deutsch. phys. Ges.*, 1907, 9, 165) found that in the best vacuum attainable in his time, fresh surfaces of metals did show a slight temperature effect, but this disappeared on outgassing. Hence the production of the Joshi effect only in the presence of the gas and its dependence on the temperature is of significance for an elucidation of its mechanism.

A critical examination of Joshi's theory of the phenomenon (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.* 1946, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) in the light of the foregoing results for H_2 may now be attempted.

The theory contemplates three stages, viz., (a) formation of a boundary layer on the container walls derived in part from adsorption of ions and molecules under applied fields intense enough to cause dielectric breakdown of the gas; (b) photoelectric emission of electrons from this boundary layer under external irradiation; and (c) capture of these photoelectrons by the excited neutral molecules and atoms on account of their electron affinity to form negative ions of low mobility, resulting in current diminution as a space charge effect.

FIG. 3

The discharge space under potentials causing ionisation by collision abounds in various species of particles such as normal and excited atoms and molecules of the gas, positive and negative ions, electrons etc. Destruction of metastable atoms and recombination of ions on irradiation were originally suggested by Joshi as probable factors in the production of the effect. The observation of a large % Δi in H_2 , observed in the present investigation, which according to Loeb ("Fundamental Processes of Electrical Discharge in Gases", p. 496) "gives a fairly low value of V_s (starting potential) and has no metastables" rules out the possibility of the effect being due to destruction of the metastables on irradiation. As regards the other suggestion, there is no instance

available in the literature where recombination of ions under irradiation has been observed. Further, if recombination were to occur under light, a spectral shift in the intensity or frequency of the glow in the discharge may be expected to follow. No such change has been observed so far.

The present theory of the *effect* advanced by Joshi, and outlined above, would appear to explain satisfactorily all the various features observed. Thus, the absence of the *effect* under potentials less than V_m , coupled with its development in an 'ageing' ozoniser and its diminution at higher temperatures supports Joshi's first postulate viz., formation of an adsorption-like boundary layer between the glass wall and the excited gas. The profound influence of the frequency and to a less extent, the intensity of the irradiating light on the *effect* establishes the photoelectric nature of the adsorbed layer. The observation of a large positive *effect* i. e., photoincrease of current under certain conditions, generally just below V_m of the system, may be cited as an additional evidence. It is well known that photoelectric currents from glass surface are very feeble. Whenelt and Schmerwitz (*Z. Physik*, 1929, **67**, 533) found that even when the full light from a carbon arc was allowed to fall on the surface of a glass plate $18 \times 18 \times 0.13$ mm., the currents were feeble, being of the order of 10^{-13} amp. Since the ionisation potentials of gases are well above 10 volts, their photoelectric threshold is shorter than $1234 \text{ \AA}$, and they can show no photoelectric effect under visible light. Hence, the production of the Joshi effect under visible light including the red end of the spectrum leads to the conclusion that the work function of the 'boundary layer' postulated by Joshi should be low.

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